

PATHOPHYSIOLOGY AND HISTOLOGICAL REFUTATION OF PARKINSON'S DISEASE**Mehdiyeva Sh.***Azerbaijan Medical University, Department of Neurology, Doctor of Philosophy in Medicine, Doctor Neurologist, Baku, Azerbaijan***Jafarova U.***Azerbaijan Medical University, Department of Normal Physiology, Doctor of Philosophy in Medicine, Senior Lecturer, Baku, Azerbaijan***Aliyarbayova A.***Azerbaijan Medical University, Department of Cytology, Embryology and Histology, Doctor of Philosophy in Medicine, Senior Lecturer, Baku, Azerbaijan***Gurbanova Sh.***Azerbaijan Medical University, Department of Cytology, Embryology and Histology, Assistant, Baku, Azerbaijan***Abaszade Z.***Azerbaijan Medical University, Department of Normal Physiology, Asst. Teacher, Baku, Azerbaijan***Sadigi I.***Azerbaijan Medical University, Department of Cytology, Embryology and Histology, Assistant, Baku, Azerbaijan***ABSTRACT**

The clinical diagnosis of PD is based primarily on motor features, such as a slowly progressive asymmetric resting tremor, cogwheel rigidity and bradykinesia, although non-motor features, which include anosmia, constipation, depression and REM sleep behavior disorder, can develop years before motor deficits. During later stages of the disease, additional non-motor features, such as autonomic dysfunction, pain and cognitive decline, can appear.

Keywords: parkinson's disease, pathophysiology, histology.

Pathologically, Parkinson disease (PD) is defined by loss of dopaminergic neurons in the substantia nigra pars compacta (SN) located in the midbrain and associated with Lewy bodies, which are cytoplasmic inclusions that include insoluble alpha-synuclein aggregates. However, PD is characterized by more widespread pathology in other brain regions and involves non-dopaminergic neurons as well. The clinical diagnosis of PD is based primarily on motor features, such as a slowly progressive asymmetric resting tremor, cogwheel rigidity and bradykinesia, although non-motor features, which include anosmia, constipation, depression and REM sleep behavior disorder, can develop years before motor deficits. During later stages of the disease, additional non-motor features, such as autonomic dysfunction, pain and cognitive decline, can appear [1].

Genetics and Pathophysiology: Most PD cases likely have a multifactorial etiology, resulting from the combined effects of environmental and genetic factors. Exposure to toxicant chemicals and head injury may increase the risk of PD, while certain lifestyle factors may lower risk. Genetic susceptibility factors may modify the effects of environmental exposures. Although identifiable mutations in certain genes cause PD in around 5–10% of cases, these mutations are absent in most people with PD. Moreover, the most common PD-associated genetic mutations have incomplete penetrance, indicating that other environmental or genetic factors are involved [2].

Specific genetic factors that play a major role in PD risk can be identified in a subset of PD patients. Polymeropoulos et al identified a mutation in the alpha-synuclein gene, SNCA, in association with rare families with autosomal dominant PD in 1997. Families with these high-penetrant mutations are quite rare, but

this seminal discovery led to the recognition that alpha-synuclein comprises a major component of Lewy bodies even in sporadic PD patients. The later discovery of autosomal dominant PD families with alpha-synuclein gene duplications or triplications added to other data indicating that high levels of alpha-synuclein contribute to the pathogenesis of PD [3].

Mutations in the PARKIN and PINK1 genes are causes of early-onset autosomal recessive PD. Both PARKIN and PINK1 have been linked to a cellular pathway involving the preferential degradation in lysosomes of dysfunctional mitochondria through macroautophagy, a process termed “mitophagy”. Loss of function of these genes leads to impaired mitophagy, resulting in the accumulation of dysfunctional mitochondria. PARKIN also indirectly regulates levels of an important transcriptional regulator, PGC-1alpha, which coordinately regulates the expression of genes required for mitochondrial biogenesis as well as multiple antioxidant defenses. PGC-1alpha levels also are low in sporadic PD, suggesting that these data are relevant beyond rare genetic forms of PD. These genetic links to both mitochondrial degradation and to mitochondrial biogenesis implicate dysfunction of mitochondrial turnover in PD [1,3,4].

Histopathology of Parkinson's disease: Macroscopically, the brain in idiopathic PD is often unremarkable with mild atrophy of the frontal cortex and ventricular dilation in some cases. The main distinctive morphological change in the PD brain is observed in transverse sections of the brainstem, where almost all cases present with loss of the darkly pigmented area in the substantia nigra pars compacta (SNpc) and locus coeruleus. This pigmentation loss directly correlates with the death of dopaminergic (DA) neuromelanin-

containing neurons in the SNpc and noradrenergic neurons in the locus coeruleus. Cell death in the SNpc is mostly restricted to a specific group of neuromelanin-

containing dopaminergic neurons, namely the A9 neurons, while other neuronal and glial cell types are largely spared (Figure 1).

Figure 1 Coronal section at the level of the substantia nigra pars compacta (SNpc) in a control (A and B) and a PD brain (C and D) stained by hematoxylin and eosin.

Quantitative morphometric studies in postmortem PD brains have calculated approximately 30% loss of DA neurons in the SNpc by motor symptom onset, adjusting for age. After the motor symptoms appear, nigral DA neuron loss increases up to 60% or higher and strongly correlates with the severity of motor features and disease duration. The result of this remarkable cell loss is the denervation of the nigrostriatal pathway, leading to diminished dopamine levels in the striatum. The reduction of dopaminergic signaling is considered responsible for the appearance of the cardinal motor symptoms in PD. Recent work has shown that nerve cell death in the SNpc is preceded by the loss of axon terminals projecting to the striatum. Mechanistically, the early neuron and axon terminal loss observed in PD suggests a substantial preclinical stage that predates the onset of symptoms by several years [5,6].

Immunological changes in iIbd: Parkinson's disease (PD) is the most common neurodegenerative movement disorder and is characterised by the progressive development of bradykinesia, muscular rigidity, rest tremor, and postural instability. The cardinal motor features result from the progressive loss of dopaminergic (DA) neurons in the substantia nigra pars compacta (SNc). A neuropathological hallmark of PD are neuronal protein aggregates termed Lewy bodies (LBs) (Fig. 1a) [7]. LBs are composed of vesicular membrane structures and dysmorphic organelles in conjunction with protein aggregates containing alpha-Synuclein as the main component (α Syn) [8,9]. Following clinical reports [10], a recent immunohistochemical study assessing the abundance of the inflammation-associated Toll-like-Receptor 2 (TLR-2) showed increased numbers of TLR-2-positive microglia in the iLBD SNc compared to PD [11], suggesting inflammatory changes occur at early stages and prior to the development of PD symptoms. By contrast, there was a progressive increase from control to PD in the numbers of

CD68-positive microglia/macrophages, a marker associated with phagocytosis, although an increase in the number of microglia was not identified [8,9]. Another piece of evidence suggesting early immunological changes came from the work of Galioano-Landeira et al. The authors found that CD8-positive T-lymphocytes were increased in the SNc of PD cases compared to the control group, whereas CD4-positive T cells remained unchanged [12]. Most notably, a robust infiltration of CD8-positive T-cells has been observed prior to the appearance of LBP (Braak Stage 1) and in the absence of DA cell death. CD8-positive T-cells were found to be equipped with cytolytic enzymes (granzymes A, B and K) and proinflammatory cytokines (interferon gamma) with phenotypic differences between early and late stages. A high proportion of nigral CD8 T cells were identified as tissue-resident memory T cells. These results identified a substantial nigral cytotoxic CD8-T-cell infiltration as an early pathogenic event preceding LBP and DA cell death in PD. This further highlights microenvironmental changes which may impact later nigral cell survival [13].

Discussion: It is well established that while Parkinson's disease pathologically manifests in the CNS with aggregation of α -synuclein as Lewy bodies and Lewy neurites, this pathology can also be found in the peripheral nervous system. Peripheral Lewy-type synucleinopathy objects (LTS) are present in PD, suggesting its utility as a diagnostic and prognostic biomarker [14]. Previous studies have shown that the expert neuropathologist semi-quantitative scoring of immunohistochemically stained WSI from PD patients, based on LTS density in the submandibular gland has high specificity in diagnosing PD, but suboptimal sensitivity [15].

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